

DESIGNING HUMAN MACHINE INTERFACE FOR DNA COMPUTING

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Abstract— The biological DNA (Deoxyribose Nucleic Acid) is being increasingly considered as an alternative processor to a silicon chip. DNA-based logic circuits are an attractive alternative to silicon-integrated circuits in specific control applications. Developing models for Boolean operations using DNA strands requires computer science and biochemistry expertise. However, there is a vast gap between the user who needs computation using DNA and the various DNA operations to be carried out with the help of Microarray, Microtiter plate and their respective Reader. In this paper, an HMI (Human machine interaction) is modelled for solving Boolean logic circuit and combinatorial optimization problems. An HMI is designed with the digital screen as the interface between the user and the bio-operations in the wet lab. The interface transforms the input from the user to DNA strands and the bio-operations to be carried out to achieve the desired solution. An attempt is made in this paper to design HMI for getting the inputs, followed by the DNA encoding of the inputs. The various bio-operational steps to be carried out in the wet lab and finally to read the output from the Microarray or Microtiter plate Reader and to be viewed in the digital screen by the user.

Keywords— DNA Computing, Human Machine interface, Boolean operations, Logical gates, DNA strand, Multiple travelling salesperson problem

I. INTRODUCTION

DNA computing has emerged as one of the emerging multi-discipline research areas. There are varieties of methods by which a DNA strand can be used as a computational tool. Adleman first developed a molecular computing technique for solving Hamiltonian Path Problem (HPP) [1]. This motivated researchers to utilise DNA for solving computationally difficult problems. Many authors have contributed to solving different combinatorial optimization problems like shortest path problem [3], [5], [6], Travelling salesperson problem [8], Knapsack problem [11], Multiple Travelling salesperson problems [15], Freeze Tag problem [17] using DNA strands. Different techniques like length-based DNA computing, and concentration-controlled DNA computing are used for obtaining near-optimal solution. Similarly, inherent parallelism in DNA was utilized by many researchers in constructing Boolean circuits. The major challenge faced by users in using DNA strands for computation is that different techniques, different bio-operations, and different encoding methods are followed for different problem. Also, a bio-technologist must carry out all the bio-operations in the wet lab. To address this problem, in this paper, a digital screen HMI is designed for the logic circuit and combinatorial optimization problem. The proposed HMI gets the input by clicking the options on the screen and navigating to the next step. Also, HMI encodes the data given by the user to DNA strands and the sequence of bio-operations required for the bio-technologist. After completion by the bio-technologist, the result will be read and displayed on the digital screen.

II. ORGANIZATION OF DNA COMPUTING

A. DNA Computing and its operation

All living cells have DNA is a sequence with lots of information. DNA presents features of living being to subsequent progeny. Ten trillion molecules of DNA occupy a small space of a tiny ball. DNA strands have the capacity for parallel processing. Each of these strands can process information simultaneously, and therefore ten trillion operations can be performed in a small area. Scientists have found a new methodology for computing using DNA [13].

Computing which includes Biochemistry and molecular biology along with molecules of DNA, is an alternate to silicon-based computer technologies [10]. DNA strands are viewed as a chain of nucleotides or bases. The four bases of a DNA are Adenine, Cytosine, Guanine and Thymine, and denoted as A, C, G and T in short. Each DNA strand has 5' and 3' ends according to its chemical properties. Bonds of hydrogen between couples of bases are created. G binds itself with C and A binds itself with T, which is how couple-wise binding takes place. Denaturing, annealing, polymerase chain reaction (PCR), ligation, gel electrophoresis and cloning are some of the biological processes that can be carried out on DNA strands.

- Denaturing is a heating process which disintegrates the double-stranded DNA into two single strands. Annealing is cooling (hybridize) the solution with single strands to bind together with complementary strands to form double-stranded DNA. This operation is a reverse operation to Denaturing.
- Ligation is repairing double-stranded DNA. If there is any discontinuity occurs in the single strand, then DNA ligase is used for repairing.
- To arrange DNA strands by its length Gel Electrophoresis technique is used. In this process, molecules which carry a negative charge are allowed to move in a porous nature gel. Molecules get attracted to the anode because it carries a negative charge. The DNA strands move at a rate proportional to their length, so longer strands move slower than the shorter strands.
- To amplify DNA stands exponentially, Polymerase chain Reaction or PCR is used. During the chemical reaction, each cycle doubles the number of strands leading to exponential growth.

B. Why HMI in DNA Computing?

DNA Computing involves encoding data into DNA strands. Following this encoding, laboratory techniques of molecular biology operations called bio-operations mentioned above are used to manipulate DNA strand in micro-titre, which will be carried out in a wet laboratory. For each bio-operation, a human (or Robot), a skilled bio-technologist and a machine are required to carry out the operation. Hence, an interface is required if a user wants to do any computation with DNA strands. In this paper, an attempt is made to model an interface for solving two types of problems one is solving Boolean operations, and the other one is combinatorial optimization problems. Here the interface will be a digital screen where the inputs are given, and the software running will convert the inputs to DNA strands which a specialist uses to solve in a wet LAB. The result obtained will be fed again to the digital screen to be viewed by the user as shown in Fig.1

Fig.1.HMI for DNA Computing

C. Microarray

DNA microarray, as in Fig.2 is termed as DNA chip, gene chips, gene arrays, DNA arrays and biochips. Fluorescently labelled target DNA sequences are attached to a substratum and then probed with a known DNA sequence. Hybridization occurs between target sequences and a probe sequence to

generate a signal. The total strength of the signal at every spot, depends upon the amount of target sample binding to the probe strand available on that spot.

Fig.2 Microarray

D. *Microarray Scanner or Reader*

The microarray scanner or reader device, as in Fig.3, consists of lasers, a special microscope, and a camera. This device will be used as the last step before analysis. The DNA material in the microarray is excited by the laser scanner as it is labelled with fluorescents. A digital image of the array is created by the microscope and camera. The intensity red-to-green fluorescent ratio is calculated in each microarray spot by a software and the resultant data is stored in a computer system.

Fig.3. Microarray scanner

E. *Microtiter Plate*

A microtiter plate is a flat plate having several "wells" where each well mimics a small test tube. The wells in the microplate are organized as rectangular matrix ordered in a 2:3 to have 6, 24, 96, 384 or even 1536 sample wells. Each well can be either circular or square which can hold somewhere around tens of nanoliters to several milliliters of liquid. For compound storage applications square wells with close fitting silicone cap-mats are preferred. Microplates can be kept at low temperatures for long periods. In life science research microplates are used for filtration, optical detection, reaction mixing, separation, storage or cell culture.

F. *Microtiter Reader*

A micro-plate reader is a device used to analyze biological, physical, and chemical reactions, properties of all biological specimens within the wells. The plates consist of numerous wells which have the DNA stands for the analysis process. In all wells, different reactions can take place which helps in the separate assessment of all types of analytes. Also, this separation helps in the progression of biochemical processes, which are transformed into optical signals. The microplate reader detects these signals and, thus,

quantifies the data from the specimen. Microplate reader provides all researchers and scientists to reduce operational time and save reagent costs. This helps the researchers to spend more time to the data analysis and to generate good results. In the microplate reader, each assay is between the 5 and 50-micron litre per well.

G. *Molecular Beacon*

Molecular beacons (MB) are single-stranded DNA probes. Each probe has a stem and a loop structure. The loop structure is created with the complementary probe sequence of a target sequence. The stem is formed by bonding with the complementary nucleotide sequence present on either side of the probe sequence. Also, on both sides of the stem quencher and fluorophore are attached. When the two ends of the MB stem are kept near each other, fluorophores will be quenched during energy transfer. In this situation, MB is “dark”. If the MB loop encounters its target sequence, it undergoes hybridization in the loop structure, forcing the fluorophore and quencher away. Immediately, MB changes from “dark” to “bright”. This is called fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET). The major advantage of MB is the Molecular recognition specificity. They are highly accurate in hybridization, so they can ignore target sequences that differ even by a single nucleotide [2][4]. The hybridization of the MB with the target is shown in Fig.4

Fig. 4. Hybridization of the MB with the target

III.HMI MODEL FOR SOLVING LOGIC CIRCUIT USING DNA

DNA molecules are increasingly attempted for employment in computational processes. There are many methods available in the literature for realizing logic circuits using DNA [7] [9]. Zoraida et al. proposed a methodology to convert the truth table to DNA logic circuit is considered in this paper [16]. DNA logic circuit is nothing but a sequence of nucleotides. Obtained DNA strand will be fixed on the Microarray, which acts as the logic circuit. The input for these DNA Logic circuits is the Molecular Beacon (MB) [12]. For each input variable, an input sequence is assigned. Two or more sequences representing the inputs of the DNA logic circuit I_1, I_2, \dots, I_n will be in the loop portion of the MB. After adding the input MB to the DNA logic circuit, annealing takes place, and there will be a change in MB. In this methodology, the fluorescence always represents 1 and the dark represents 0. The intensity occurring in the microarray will be read by the microarray reader from which the output can be recognized. Considering the above procedure, an HMI is modelled as shown in Fig.5 to choose logic circuit interface or combinatorial optimization interface.

Fig. 5. Interface for choosing the problem

Fig. 6. Interface for logic circuit to get input from the user.

If the logical circuit interface is selected, the system will navigate to the screen as shown in Fig.6 to get the inputs from the user.

In this interface, the user gives the truth table of the logic circuit to be carried out through the digital screen. The interface initially gets the number of inputs and output for the logic circuit and the output for each min term in the truth table[14]. A software for converting the Truth table of the logic circuit to DNA strand logic circuit and the DNA MB inputs to the DNA logic circuit is created. Created DNA strands which acts as the DNA logic circuit and the input MB will be handed over to a specialist to prepare the DNA chip (Microarray). In the DNA chip the DNA input MB is made to hybridize with the strand fixed in the Microarray. The result obtained from the microarray is read by Microarray Scanner and will be passed on to the digital screen which can be viewed by the user as shown in Fig.7

Fig. 7. Interface for logic circuit to see the output by the user

A. Constructing DNA Logic Circuit

This session describes a strategy for constructing DNA logic circuits using with MB as inputs. The two values $I=0$ and $I=1$ of binary Boolean variable I is denoted as I_0 and I_1 . I_1 and I_2 are the two inputs of a gate in the Boolean circuit. Four unique DNA strand is taken to represent logical 0 as I_1^0 and I_2^0 for the two inputs I_1 and I_2 and to represent logical 1 as I_1^1 and I_2^1 for the two inputs I_1 and I_2 . The respective complements of the chosen strands are represented as $\overline{I_1^0}$, $\overline{I_2^0}$, $\overline{I_1^1}$ and $\overline{I_2^1}$. So for a two-input gate only four strands are required. Coloured pattern representation for $I_1^0, I_2^0, I_1^1, I_2^1, \overline{I_1^0}, \overline{I_2^0}, \overline{I_1^1}$ and $\overline{I_2^1}$ is followed in this paper for visualizing the implementation instead of representing the actual strands. Fig.8 shows the patterns and Boolean inputs and their complements

Fig.8. DNA coloured Pattern representation

A general form of truth table for two-input circuit is shown in Table 1. I_1 and I_2 are the inputs and Z_1 to Z_4 are the outputs

Table 1 Truth Table for two-input gates

I_2	I_1	Z_i
	1	
0	0	Z_1
0	1	Z_2
1	0	Z_3
1	1	Z_4

In the construction of DNA logic circuit, the rows having their output $Z_i = 1$ ($i = 1$ to 4) are selected. First row having $Z_i = 1$ is taken and its I_1 and I_2 values are stored in an array. Moving on to next row with $Z_i = 1$, its I_1 value is compared with the last value stored in the array. If I_1 value is same as the last value in the array, I_2 of the current row is added to the array. Otherwise, “*” followed by the two values I_1 and I_2 of the current row is added to the array. The same procedure is repeated for the remaining rows having Z_i value as 1. Finally, each value in the array is replaced with the corresponding complementary strand as shown in Fig.8. The symbol “*” is replaced by the blocker sequence. The obtained strand is the required DNA Boolean circuit which performs the operation.

B. Inputs of the DNA logic circuit

DNA Boolean circuit strand obtained from the above procedure will be fixed on the surface at the 3’end of the microarray. MB is the input for these DNA circuits. Two DNA sequences representing the inputs of the circuit I_1 and I_2 are placed in the loop portion of the MB. Changes that happened after introducing the MB represent the results of the DNA circuit. In this operation, the fluorescence always represents 1, and the dark represents 0. The MB inputs for any Boolean circuit having their inputs I_1 and I_2 is presented in Fig.9. The MB has only one sequence in case of NOT and BUFFER gate in the loop portion i.e. the input I_1 of the circuit. With the above process, DNA strands generated will be used by the wet lab. The interface modelled as in Fig 1 will be a mediator between the user and the Wet lab.

Fig. 9. MB inputs of the gates

IV. HMI MODEL FOR SOLVING OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM USING DNA

Ever Since Adleman the father of DNA computing published paper for solving Hamiltonian Path Problem (HPP) using DNA, researchers attempted to solve computationally difficult problems with molecules [1]. Many authors contributed for solving different optimization problem like shortest path problem [3], minimum spanning tree[16], travelling salesperson problem[8], knapsack problem[11] and many more. Each problem has its inputs and methodology to achieve the optimal solution. In the case of a Multiple travelling salesperson problem, the inputs will be a number of cities, the edges between the cities, the number of salespersons, and the home node (Depot). In order to solve this problem using DNA, each input need to be encoded with DNA strands and by applying different bio-operations the appropriate optimal solution can be obtained. Since the user is not aware of different encoding methods and DNA operations, there is need for an interface so that the input from the user can be received for a particular problem using the digital screen interface. Once the input is received, encoding and the sequence of bio-operations that need to be carried out will be generated by the interface and will be handed over to a bio-technologist to implement the process. Finally, the optimal solution will be displayed on the digital screen. With these considerations, a digital screen HMI is modelled for solving combinatorial optimization problems as shown in Fig.10.

Fig. 10. Interface for choosing multiple travelling salesperson problem

In this Digital screen HMI, a drop-down menu displays the various problems to solve in a DNA computer. After a problem is selected on the screen, the corresponding input required for solving the problem will be requested by the HMI to the user. Once the user supplies all the inputs, encoding of the input to DNA strands will be carried out by the software. For example, as in Fig.10 if Multiple travelling sales person problem is clicked, the system will navigate to a screen as shown in Fig.11 where the inputs needed for the problem is displayed. The number of cities, number of sales people, the home city (Depot) is requested from the user. Apart from these data the edges between each city are received from the user by the adjacency matrix and the distance between each edge is received by the distance matrix as shown in Fig.11

Fig. 11. Interface to get input from the user

An instance with seven cities ($C_i, i = 1$ to 7) and three salespersons is considered in this interface as shown in Fig.12. City 7 is the home node (Depot). From city 7 all the three salespersons start and end their tour.

Different Methodologies are available in the literature for solving MTSP. In this interface, the methodology discussed by the author[14] is considered. For each city, C_i

Fig. 12. The graph corresponding to MTSP with 7 cities and 3 salespersons

has been assigned a unique DNA single strand (cs) with a fixed length of 20 bases having similar melting temperature is synthesized. For city C_7 (Depot) alone, a home city strand (hcs) of 30 bases is synthesized.

A length of 30 bases for C_7 is assigned to easily separate the strands by length for each possible change in the number of salespersons. Also, for each distance, a unique

Fig. 13. Encoding City, Edge, and distance sequence for seven-city MTSP

distance sequence(ds) of length 20 bases with varying melting temperature is generated. Lower melting temperature for smaller distance and higher temperature for longer distances is assigned. Bio-chemical operations are applied on these city and distance strands and the path that visits all the cities with lower melting temperature will be the more economical path. The DNA sequence for each city and for each unique distance DNA sequences are generated and displayed on the digital screen as shown in Fig. 13 after the “Run” button is clicked in Fig.11.

Sequence of bio-operation are applied on these generated DNA strands by the bio-technologist to obtain the optimal solution. Initial pool is generated using the city strands and road strands and allowed to hybridize to the complement road strand. Ligation operation are carried out for repairing any discontinuity in the DNA strand. Gel electrophoresis operation are applied to separate the strands with different length followed by affinity purification. As discussed in the paper [15] the DNA strands for cities, distance and roads are generated with varying melting temperature. Denatured temperature gradient (DTG-PCR) and Temperature gradient gel electrophoresis (TGGE) operations are carried out to filter the most economical

path. Obtained economical path are cloned and sequenced to identify the optimum solution. This path will be fed to the system and will be displayed in the digital screen as shown in the Fig.14.

Fig. 14. Interface for viewing the output by the user

V. CONCLUSION

DNA computing has emerged as one of the emerging multi-discipline research areas. Algorithms employing DNA for solving optimization problems has gradually gained momentum. Since the user is unaware of using DNA strands and encoding data to DNA strands there is a need for an interface to bridge the user and biosystems. An interface model is attempted for the first time for DNA computing so that user with no knowledge on DNA strands can solve the problem using DNA. In this paper, specific problems like realizing Boolean operators and solving hard computational problems are considered. This model can be extended to all other domains like DNA cryptography and steganography, DNA Authentication and DNA storage.

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